

Fostering Computational Thinking skills in middle school students using CT@Home mobile application

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Abstract—Computational thinking skills are recognised as the necessary 21st century competency among learners of various levels. There is an increase in awareness on the potential benefits of introducing computational thinking (CT) skills in the school level curriculum. The existing solutions like block-based activities, AR-VR apps, game-based learning solutions require more relatable and authentic learning contexts. The present study conducted with 49 middle school students (7th and 8th) traces how an educational application called CT@Home can be used to foster logical thinking and CT skills by providing authentic learning experiences through a relevant context which is meaningful to the learner. We investigated the effectiveness of the application around three specific constructs: learning gain, usability, and self-perception. The results suggest that applications like CT@Home which can provide context-based learning, helps in building a positive perception towards learning CT skills among middle school students. Finally, we also discuss some of the important challenges that students faced while interacting with the CT@Home application.

Index Terms—Computational Thinking, Logical thinking, Usability, Learning Gain, Context-based learning, Authentic learning

I. INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Computational Thinking (CT) is defined as “the thought processes involved in formulating problems and their solutions so that the solutions are represented in a form that can be effectively carried out by an information-processing agent” by Cuny–Snyder–Wing [1].

Additionally, CT is a problem- solving approach used in computer science that involves breaking down complex problems into smaller, more manageable parts or patterns and developing algorithms or step-by-step procedures to solve them. It involves a set of skills and thought processes, including abstraction, decomposition, pattern recognition, and algorithmic design, that can be applied to a wide range of problems, even beyond those typically encountered in computer science. The proponents of this theory claim that the skills are generalizable across disciplines [2] as they are not only limited to programming or coding; rather, computational thinking can be used to approach and solve problems in any field, from science and engineering to social sciences and humanities.

Also, the key argument of applying CT practices is to reason at multiple levels of abstraction while solving problems [3].

As a skill, CT helps students develop problem-solving abilities, logical reasoning, and creativity. Additionally, it can also inform students about the effective use of technology. Hence, by learning it in schools, students can be prepared for the challenges in the real world [3]. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in using educational technology to teach CT concepts, as seen from the increasing number of CT papers [4].

There are multiple frameworks that are used to characterize CT. These frameworks can be broadly seen as a) core programming-related frameworks, and b) generalised frameworks that are aimed at general problem-solving skills. The former kind of framework suggested by Brennan and Resnick, categorizes CT in terms of concepts, practices, and perspectives which are related to programming. Similar categorizations are available in the works of other authors in the domain. Subsequently, the later frameworks which focus on problem-solving skills categorize it as abstractions, decomposition, logical thinking, and so on. The frameworks such as those proposed by Sellby and Woollard, and others have similar categorizations [5].

ICT applications are often used to facilitate learning, particularly for school students. One such example can be seen in the review by Fagerlund et. al.,[6] on teaching CT in programming using Scratch. This review was scoped to teaching programming concepts that foster the development of CT skills in students. Additional CT interventions have also been used for other applications (LEGO MINDSTORMS, CTSiM platform, Alice, etc.). Shute et al. provides a synthesis of the studies done with the CT interventions for different grade levels. The tools used for these interventions were exclusively digital and were facilitated through technology in classrooms [7]. The advantages of using such tools are that it provides a unique way of self-expression through coding by providing a block-based programming environment in which students cannot make syntactic mistakes by the virtue of the design of the application [7]. Added to this, the impact of video games on the development of CT skills shows promising results

regarding the development of cognitive and attitudinal changes among elementary school children, such as promoting the learning of some CT components, improving attitudes towards computer science (CS) [8], and development of algorithmic solutions to a problem [9].

Computational thinking skills are being taught using a multitude of mobile applications. Papadakis et al., in their work, have presented a comparative analysis of the CT concepts supported by four widely used applications [10]. These applications provide learners with engaging activities and coding environments that facilitate the learning of CT concepts. They can be integrated in the curriculum to teach different CS concepts [11]. This has also been mentioned in a relatively recent review [12]. The integration of CT into curricula has also shown to be effective in STEM subjects in general, with game design-based instructional methods being one of the most popular ones [13]. Examples include the integration of MIT app inventor to teach mobile app development [14], and as a game-based classroom course for 3rd and 4th-grade students [15].

Connecting students' knowledge with the real world is crucial for developing logical reasoning skills and teaching the concept of looping. This integration of knowledge and the real world is known as authentic learning, which provides students with a more meaningful and relevant learning experience [16-17]. The authentic context also promotes learning among students[18-19]. This approach not only fosters their understanding of the concepts but also motivates them to continue learning and apply their knowledge to solve real-world problems [20-21].

The present study focused on analyzing how a mobile-based application called CT@Home can be utilized to support teaching of the conditional and loop concepts in CT in an authentic context. The context used was Earth hour, in which based on certain conditions like date and time, students have to use block based instructions based on concepts of looping to perform actions to switch "OFF" or "ON" the lights at a home based learning environment. We expect this study will also contribute towards understanding the different elements of design that are required to develop mobile-based learning applications to foster CT skills in students and help educators to design more effective educational technology tools.

The present study focuses on how middle school students can be engaged in CT related activities using CT@Home mobile application. It looks at how students can learn computer science concepts like loops, nested loops, and conditionals through apps, in an authentic real-life context of celebrating Earth hour and saving home energy by coding the instructions for IoT (Internet of Things) based on the home appliances that were represented in the application. The present study was conducted as part of the Research Methodology in Educational Technology course.

The remaining part of this paper is organized in the following manner, first we discussed the design of CT@Home mobile application, followed by the description of its implementation in the real-life scenario. Further, we present the results in

the form of learning gains of the students, their perceptions of CT and the usability of the application's interface. These results are followed by discussion and conclusion section where applicability of CT@Home in fostering the CT skills is discussed.

II. DESIGN OF CT@HOME

CT@Home is an android based application to help novice students typically in the middle school level, to develop introductory logical and computational thinking (CT) skills. The pedagogy used in CT@Home is based on learning by doing and computational tasks, which supports to improve logical thinking skills while solving CT problems. It allows learners to work at their own pace and be actively engaged in the learning process, where the learner is engaged in introductory CT activities in the context of their familiar surroundings, at home.

The CT@Home application has three levels (Fig.1). In level 1, the learners can navigate through different rooms in a house using direction buttons. Each room has different IoT devices (eg. TV) which can be manipulated using actions (move right, left, up and bottom), after checking conditions (eg. whether TV is switched ON or OFF) using different sensors. The level 2 activity is intended to develop logical and computational thinking skills in learners through the concept of Earth hour which takes place annually on the last Saturday of March. In this level, three types of sensors (Date, Time and light) are used to programme the bulbs in a room using pseudocode so that they go OFF on 26th of every month from 8:30 pm to 9:30 pm. Necessary prompts were also given for scaffolding purposes for the learners in each step. The activity involves logically coding the steps to use the correct sensors, conditions and actions to turn off the lights for one hour (Fig.2).

Using the application, learners get a deeper understanding of the different steps involved in computational thinking applied at different scenarios and observing the outcomes (Table 1).

TABLE I
DIFFERENT STEPS INVOLVED IN CT AND THE CORRESPONDING TASKS PERFORMED IN LEVEL 2 OF CT@HOME

Steps involved in CT	Corresponding tasks in Level 2 of CT@Home
Decomposition (breaking down a complex problem into smaller, more manageable parts)	Identifying the steps involved like choosing the date, time and actions
Pattern recognition (identifying connections between different parts of each task)	Selection of proper SENSOR first, followed by CONDITION and then ACTION in each step
Abstraction (identify the important information required to solve the task)	Selection of exact date, time and actions
Algorithmic thinking (defining a step-by-step solution to the problem that can be replicated for a predictable and reliable outcome)	Steps followed in executing pseudocode to turn the bulbs ON and OFF to celebrate Earth hour

The Level 3 of the application was focused on applying the CT skills by learners to set up a security system using motion sensors and home appliances within rooms in a house.

Fig. 1. Screenshot of CT@Home

Fig. 2. Screenshot of CT@Home (Level 2)

The different IoT objects can be manipulated using actions after checking the conditions using sensors. The CT@Home application was thus designed to increase the relevance of CT among students in their everyday contexts and aims to make CT more accessible and useful to a wider range of students. While the application offers three levels of scaffolded learning experiences, this study was limited to Level 2 due to time and technical constraints. Levels 1 and 3 of the CT@Home application were excluded from the study, as they involve physical movement within an empty room. The decision to exclude these levels was made in light of the logistical challenges associated with creating a suitable environment for Level 1 and Level 3, including the need for an empty room and the additional time required for setup and study.

III. METHODS

A. Research Questions

The primary goal of CT@Home mobile application is to assist middle school students who are new to computational thinking (CT) in developing fundamental skills of logical reasoning and problem-solving. Through the present study, the authors try to find answers to the following research questions: What is the effect of CT@home on logical thinking of middle school students? What is the usability of CT@Home application in facilitating tasks related to logical thinking skills? What are the middle school students' perception about CT skills?

B. Participants

A total of 49 students (34 girls and 15 boys), studying in grades 7th and 8th in schools affiliated to Maharashtra SSC board participated in the study. Most of the students were proficient in Hindi and Marathi and could understand English as well.

C. Procedure

The entire study was conducted in two batches within a closed room. At the beginning of the study, numbers from 1- 49 were randomly assigned to each participant and they were asked to identify themselves on all documents using only this number. A random sampling technique was followed (Fig.3) to select participants in each batch. Each participant individually participated in the study, which was carried out for about 1.5 hours. At first the study on the effect of CT@Home on logical thinking was carried out followed by usability of the application and study on students' perception about CT skills. The participants and their parents had signed the necessary assent and consent forms before the study. All researchers were present throughout the study to explain the study procedure, provide necessary instructions, facilitate and address the concerns raised by the participants during the study. An introductory video on Earth hour (in English) was shown to all participants and explanation on the video was given in Marathi (mother tongue of students) before the study. The instructions were given in both English and Marathi languages.

Fig. 3. Design of the conducted study

D. Data sources and instruments

(a) To assess the changes in logical and CT skills, the students responded to a pre-test and post-test (3 puzzle-based questions each) during the study. After the pre-test, the participants were allowed to explore the CT@Home app (Level 2) installed in tablet PCs. The questions for both pre-test and post-test were framed based on the Computational Thinking Test (CTt) developed by Román-González et al., 2017[22]. A primary face validity of the instrument could only be done due to limitation in time. In the study, the students were given 20 minutes to complete each test and most of the participants completed their writing prompts within 10-15 minutes.

(b) To understand the usability of CT@Home application in facilitating tasks related to logical thinking skills, a modified version of System Usability Scale developed by Putnam et al., 2020 was used[23]. The questionnaire consisted of 10 different statements for which each participant has to mark his/her most appropriate response. The responses of each participant were analyzed on a 5-point Likert scale.

(c) To understand the students' perception of CT skills, a survey was conducted with 15 statements for which each participant has to mark his/her most appropriate response (Kong et al., 2018)[24]. The instrument was originally designed to study the perception of students towards programming. The responses of each participant were analyzed on a 5-point Likert

scale.

IV. RESULTS

The learning gain was computed using Hake's formula given by $(S_{post} - S_{pre}) / (S_{max} - S_{pre})$, where S_{post} represents the posttest score, S_{pre} represents the pre-test score and S_{max} represents the total score of the test[25]. The learning gain of 27 participants could not be included for further analysis as they achieved perfect scores in both pretest and post-test[26]. The analysis was carried out for the remaining 22 participants and the normalized Hake's learning gain was computed for the participants (Mean= 0.8257, SD=0.35). The learning gain indicated that CT@Home plays a positive role in learning computational thinking skills.

The data of pre-test (Mean= 2.38, SD=0.78) and post-test (Mean= 2.89, SD=0.3) was observed to violate the normality and equal variance assumption required for t-test. Hence, a Wilcoxon signed rank test was performed between the scores of pre-test and post-test. The test revealed a significant difference between the scores of pre-test and post-test mean ($z = 3.96$, $p < .001$) with effect size ($r = 0.40$).

The reliable instrument System Usability Scale (SUS) was used for measuring the usability. The SUS contains 10 statements. Participants were supposed to score those 10 statements with one of the five responses that range from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree in a 5 point Likert scale. In SUS, odd number statements and even number statements are phrased positively and negatively[27].

All 10 SUS statements were modified by adapting them as per the participants' level of understanding[28]. Two examples of original and modified SUS statements are as follows:

Original Statement 1: I think that I would like to use this system frequently

Modified Statement 1: If I had this [app] on my phone, I think that I would like to play it a lot

Original Statement 2: I found the system unnecessarily complex.

Modified Statement 2: I was confused many times when I was playing [app]

The result shows that positive statements were scored between agree to strongly agree and the negative statements were scored between disagree to neither agree or disagree (Fig.4.). Participants' responses to these statements were converted to SUS score using the standard formula $((\text{rating of odd questions}) - 5) + (25 - (\text{rating of even questions})) * 2.5$. [29] SUS score of CT@Home app (Mean= 61.37, SD= 13.891) is considered as good [30], however, no formal interview was conducted but an informal conversation with participants proved useful to validate the score as good.

The perception about CT skills was conducted via a perception survey comprising 15 statements (Fig.5.). Statements were classified into four categories: meaningfulness, impact, creative self-efficacy, programming self-efficacy and in each category 4, 3, 3, 5 statements respectively (Fig.6.). Perception survey form was based on a 5 point Likert scale. The statements ranged from Strongly Disagree to Strongly

Fig. 4. SUS survey analysis of CT@Home app. Orange bars indicate positively phrased questions, such as statement “If I had this [app] on my phone, I think that I would like to play it a lot” and blue bars indicate negative phrasing of the same, such as statement “If I had this [app] on my phone, I think that I would like to play it a lot” . The longer orange bars and shorter blue bars indicate internal validity of the instrument as well the overall positive sentiment associated with the instrument.

Agree with 0 to 5 score respectively. One statement from each category are as follows: Category: Meaningfulness Statement 1. Computational Thinking (CT) is useful to me. Category: Impact Statement 5. I want to use Computational Thinking (CT) to help solve problems in the world. Category: Creative self-efficacy Statement 8. I would like to design things using Computational Thinking (CT). Category: Programming self-efficacy Statement 12. I can learn how to do Computational Thinking (CT). The participant’s response was taken after the post-test. The score of perception about CT skills which is based on 5 point Likert scale (Mean=4.40, SD= 0.395)

Fig. 5. Average user rating for perception of computational thinking. X-axis represents perception survey statements and y-axis represents the average perception rating received for each statement. Blue bars represent meaningfulness, orange bars represent impact, green bars represent creative self-efficacy, yellow bars represent programming self-efficacy.

Fig. 6. Mean user rating for subsection of perception survey. X-axis represents categories of perception survey statements and y-axis represents the average rating received for each category. Blue bars represent meaningfulness, orange bars represent impact, green bars represent creative self-efficacy, yellow bars represent programming self-efficacy.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this study, an android application named ‘CT@Home’ was designed to foster middle school students’ computational thinking skills using relevant real life contexts/scenarios. The application was designed such that it could be used without any support from the instructor. From the three levels as designed in the application, level-2 constituting use of IoT devices in the Earth Hour context, was tested with 49 students of grade 7 and 8, enrolled in Maharashtra SSC board, with the objective to improve students’ logical thinking skills while solving CT problems and their perception towards CT.

From the findings of the study, the significant difference between pre-test and post-test scores and a high learning gain (0.82), implies improvement in the students’ learning post playing with the application. However, while calculating the learning gain, the scores of a large number of participants scoring maximum marks in both pre and posttests, were excluded. Additionally, a considerable high Total Average Perception Score (4.39) along with a high learning gain, indicate the outcome of the study in a desirable direction. Despite the positive results, we remain cautious about the interpretation, as the students’ perception about CT could be based upon their experience with the application (technological familiarity), rather than their perception about CT in isolation. It might be because the students were hearing the term for the first time, as CT is still not formally part of the standardized curriculum. Even though the researchers tried to introduce the concept before letting them fill the perception questionnaire, there is a reasonable chance they might have reflected on the sum total of their experience using the app instead of reflecting on their experience with CT only.

We have used System Usability Scale (SUS) and informal observations to evaluate the usability of the application for investigating the user experience in our study. Hence, we have observed participants’ interaction with this application,

and we found usability issues, indicators of enjoyment, and engagement to understand the impact of various features of the application on students' user experience. All participants in the study attempted the questionnaire. Based on the SUS calculation formula, the mean value of SUS scores was 61.37, indicating a below average usability of the application's interface (SUS score 68 is considered average). This may be due to the fact that some features of the application were not intuitive, leading to difficulties in navigating and effectively utilizing the features of the application. Also, some design issues were observed by the study team. In the study, the "Sensor Button" was observed to include both Date and Time, resulting in confusion during user interactions. Additionally, when presented with three options, the interface accepted only the correct option without providing any error prompts. These issues were examined in the research paper, focusing on describing the observed phenomena and findings. Students were confident to play with the app, but they had to take guidance and support to understand the tasks, clarify the doubts and interact with the app. This could impact their engagement and perceived value of the study. Hence, there was a need for implicit scaffolding in the app interface. Despite these limitations, we found that even though the students encountered challenges due to some non-intuitive features in the application and many failed attempts to complete the level, they were actively engaged throughout the process and made several attempts, again indicating a positive perception of the students towards the learning process. If the content taught through the application is perceived as relevant to their studies, or problem-solving abilities, students are more likely to view computational thinking positively. Hence, it can be concluded that the use of mobile applications like CT@Home integrating relevant, everyday authentic contexts, could be used for improving students' performance and perception about computational thinking skills, as indicated by this study. Moreover, it also encourages teachers to introduce as well as use applications like CT@Home to enhance computational thinking skills among students at middle school level.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We sincerely acknowledge and express our deep gratitude to Ashutosh Raina, Prof. Sridhar Iyer, Nagesh Pokle and Sumitra Sadhukhan for their exceptional work in designing and developing the CT@Home app. Their expertise, dedication, and technical proficiency were instrumental in bringing our vision to life and creating a user-friendly interface. We also extend heartfelt thanks to our course instructors, Prof. Sridhar Iyer, Prof. Sahana Murthy, and Prof. Ritayan Mitra, of Interdisciplinary Program (IDP) Educational Technology, IIT Bombay, for their unwavering support and insightful feedback throughout the course, as well as to teaching assistants Ram Das Rai and Kabyashree Khanikar for their invaluable guidance. Lastly, we express our gratitude to research scholar Setu Maheshwari for his valuable contribution to the smooth execution of the overall study and data collection process.

Their collective efforts have significantly contributed to the success of our research endeavour.

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